

Political Manifesto, and Election Manifesto of Mental Asylum of Education

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Abstract: Political manifesto, and Election manifesto are important for all organizations to provide their political views, and to maintain democracy, along with works they would do after winning election. Mental Asylum of Education has submitted application and Widhaan in Local Level (Gauradaha Municipality), and in District Administration Offices of Jhapa, and Kathmandu, by email. Elections does happens generally once in five years, and thus, both; election manifesto, and political manifesto are discussed, so that author can stand in election as a candidate from Mental Asylum of Education.

Introduction to Election Manifesto:

Beginning from discussion of Election manifesto, author had submitted application letter to Election commission of Nepal with a simple question, "How can any person(you) be happy and satisfied?" By means of that application letter, author had intended to seek views especially of governmental employees, but not being limited only to governmental employees, and in general for all peoples. That question was to find out the source of happiness and satisfaction along with ways to be happy and satisfied beginning from their employment, workhood, and livelihood as per laws, and moralness.

That was prelude to election manifesto, as in election manifesto, author needs to work out on topics, claiming to do works after winning election, based on answers provided by individuals to be happy and satisfied. Election manifesto of individual is needed before election, where he/she (individual) describes, promises, what would he/she do, after winning election.

Once author in his facebook profile(/arjundahalard)too had written in quite bluffy way, for Political Manifesto and Election Manifesto, like as making Nepal as a International country, as peoples do think, Nepal as an internationally recognized country, probably being based on nations with whom Nepal has diplomatic ties, or being based on news and newspapers, and Youtube, where lot of international topics can be found presenting by Nepalese peoples.

Few other topics that I had mentioned in election manifesto, and political manifesto was about International Judicial Act, and Trial Procedures for the cases that hasn't been settled and solved since

the time of maoist insurgency period, and which sometimes are seen in medias, so that peoples would get justice. Justice too is an important factor, that does keeps any individual happy and satisfied, as per laws.

Political Manifesto:

Election manifesto does changes as per election, as per candidates appearing in election based on progressing time, where as Political manifesto is hard to be changed as it contains doctrine of political party. Thus we shall begin with discussion of Jholey and Hanumaney University model,(J-H University model), where a government and it's administrations itself runs like as university. In our proposed J-H university model, President would be like as Patron, Vice-President would be like as Associate or Assistant Patron, and Prime-minister as Chancellor of University, and it would depend upon, who is the working head of any nation; relying on President, or Prime-minister.

That would allow departments and commissions of Governments as per various administrations to work like as departments of university, where a head of any administration would be like as head of department of various faculties in universities. Thus in J-H university model, more outputs are likely to be seen in public administration, especially in data collection, observation and statistics, based on registration, dispatch, and works done by government for public. Employees can analyze the data, as well as publish their works and reports, based on works done.

When tiers of administration system are discussed, then again as per tiers; Like as Federal, Provincial, and Local level of Nepal, J-H university model, would still work by same procedures above, by means of departments (same like as of Ministries and departments of government).

Besides patron, and associate patron, from the rank of Chancellor each administration can work like as department of university. We haven't allowed Patron, and Associate Patron to be discussed in plurality, as President are generally discussed as patron of constitution. Similarly, it would depend upon universities of nation, if they would like to have prime-minister as Chancellor, or would like to have separate chancellor, other than that of prime-minister of nation. In local levels of Nepal, elected presidents of rural municipality, municipality, sub-metropolitan city, metropolitan city too would work like as chancellor, or vice-chancellor. In Nepal, prime-minister is generally considered as Chancellor of university, thus in J-H university model, head of each departments would be same like as of head of departments of universities, where as elected fellows would have ranks of Chancellor, Vice-President, and President.

University relies on work and outputs, which are attained by works done by administrations for peoples. Furthermore, when works done by administrations are linked to universities of nation, then that would bolster progress. For an example, in Nepal, preparation of annual reports is needed, and when individual private firms, private firms, organizations, companies, institutions are linked to universities, then besides government as university, other universities too would study and do co-ordination for more concrete result in theoretical and applicational basis.

Conclusion:

Happiness and Satisfaction in election manifesto is to find out views how can peoples be happy and satisfied, based on laws, where as J-H university model is discussed to increase the participation of employees in policy making of nation, as well as to encourage them in publication from highest level of authority to lowest level of authority. Administrations have raw data, and that helps to provide better output then that of sampling, and sample survey.

Cons:

Besides taxation, to sustain economy J-H university model has to rely on grants based on researches and outputs, which though isn't disadvantage, author thought to write it in con section, as grants aren't easily available.

References (Application Letters)

1. Arjun Dahal. (2021). Application Letters, and Other Documents. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4933945>

Comments and Actknowledgements:

Author had written several application letters in Nepali Languages, and had uploaded to Zenodo too, and this paper too is an extended(revised) form of application letter submitted to Election Commission. I don't know, if it would just be called as an translation or an paper, but I haven't received any responses from administrations.